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**A SOCIOLINGUISTIC ANALYSIS OF SELECTED HAUSA IDIOMATIC
EXPRESSIONS**

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Abstract

This paper analyzes the sociolinguistic of selected Hausa idiomatic expressions. It analyzed the Hausa idioms from a sociolinguistic point of view in the context of English as second language (L2). This offers a sociolinguistic prospect to the contribution of Hausa and culture in the sociolinguistic background of English. The data were sourced and collected orally from some competent Hausa native speakers that live in northern Nigeria, particularly in Katsina State from the context of use. A total of ten (10) Hausa idioms were analyzed using the Ethnography of Communication theory championed by Dell Hymes as theoretical framework. It studies how communication practices are shaped by and reflect cultural context. It also emphasizes the interplay between culture, language, and social interactions focusing on how communication is embedded in specific cultural settings. The key findings revealed that the usage of Hausa idioms by means of apparatus of sociolinguistics satisfies the need of Hausawa (Hausa people). It also shows its worldview. Furthermore, the paper indicates that the historical and cultural lives of Hausawa (Hausa people) can be learned and or studied through idioms. This paper proves that it is impossible to untie the link between Hausa idioms, an aspect of Hausa language, in the context of English as second language (L2). SPEAKING mnemonics of Dell Hyme renders it physically possible to analyze the data socio-linguistically and reach a conclusion of the meaning of Hausa idioms and their implications socio-linguistically.

Key words: Idioms, Sociolinguistics, SPEAKING mnemonics

Introduction

In the repertoire of any language, idiomatic expressions constitute a special category of lexical items presenting on fixed structure and a special behavior in language used. Idioms are highly culture-specific. That is why idioms are defined as "generally language specific, relatively fixed expressions where the meaning of the whole is transparent from the constituents of the world", Lewis, 19). The large chunks of idioms in all languages make them not only essential part in everyday language but also an interesting area of study. Despite the fact that idiomatic expressions are an important part of our everyday discourse, they are still neglected in language studies. Makkai, 23 opines that "the study of idiomaticity has been left widely untouched in scholarly studies which makes it one of the under-explored area of language." It is this puzzling that idioms have been so widely ignored in scholarly studies for long. Fernando, 12 too, states that "idioms as conventionalized multi word expressions have been neglected in the lexical studies of languages in comparison to other linguistic phenomenon." She stresses that this neglect is evident with respect to the functions of idiom.

Idiomatic expressions can be very difficult for people who have no or little knowledge of the socio-cultural background of the people in which this expansion emerged. Despite this, idiomatic expressions can have universal intelligibility within language. Idiom, sometimes, defy the conventional logic of grammar. Idiomatic expressions are often fixed, fossilized phrases that are not susceptible to lexical substitution.

Hausa as it is used here, refers to the language spoken by one of the major ethnic groups in Nigeria. Hausa is a Chadic language with the largest number of speakers, spoken as first language by more than seventy million people and as a second language by another millions or more people. Though, Hausa people live in vast area, especially in northern Nigeria, the

dialectal difference is are comparatively few and or insignificant. From this, we can say that Hausa speakers have at least close to 90% of mutual intelligibility", (Asmau, 18).

Like any other languages, Hausa people have rich culture and unique traditions. They also have certain wise sayings drawn from their daily live, while these wise sayings which have been passed down from one generation to the other generation offer a great insight about the beauty of language, idioms are also hilarious and bring smile to the face of a listener.

Concept of Sociolinguistics

Several definitions of Sociolinguistics abound. Dell Hymes confirms this by saying the term sociolinguistics means many things to many people, and also no one has a compendious definition of the concept Sociolinguistics.

Sociolinguistics is the study of how people use language in their everyday lives. As a field, sociolinguistics looks at how identities are manifested through the words we use and how, through the language we use to create, maintain, and adjust relationship with others. It studies the relationship between language and society and between users of a language and the structure in which they live. According to Crystal, sociolinguistics is a discipline "which studies language variation and use in relation to the cultural pattern and beliefs of men" 156. In the opinion of Holmes, sociolinguists are interested in explaining why we speak differently in different social contexts, and their major focus is identifying the social functions of language and the way it is used to convey meanings" (243). This gives an insight into the way languages work as well as relationships that exists amongst users in linguistic community. Akindele and Adegbite, define sociolinguistics as "the relationship which exists between a language or languages and the culture and traditions as well as the politics of a particular community"(267). They further assert that "it examines the interaction between the use of language and the social organizations behavior."(268). As stated by Hudson, sociolinguistics as field of linguistic study

gained prominence in the 1960s and early 1970s, (86). This indicates how recent the concept of Sociolinguistics is. Crystal gives a comprehensive definition of the term sociolinguistics as "a branch of linguistics which studies all aspects of the relationship between language and society"(489). William Labov is considered to be one of the proponents of sociolinguistics who has immense importance in its development. He is also recognized for introducing the qualitative study of language variation, change and for making the sociology of language a specific discipline.

Idiomatic Expressions

Idioms have been defined by many scholars. Here are some of the definitions. Idioms are integral and important part of any language and a reflection of culture, belief, and custom of a people", (Wright, 75). According to Eyoh, idioms are expressions whose meaning is not decipherable through knowledge of the individual meaning of the constituent word but lie subtly beyond the words and within the depth of the expression", (p1). Saeed, too, says "idioms are a syntactic pattern peculiar to a certain language and hence often untranslatable in literal equivalents into language", (p 80).

Almost all idioms are fixed in their forms and cannot be changed, altered, or varied so much that the best way to understand an idiom is to see it in the context in which it comes. McCarthy and O'Dell state that "idioms are expressions which have a meaning that is not obvious from the individual word"(6) for example, the idiom "Dinyar makaho ta nuna aljihunsa" means what is rightly yours should be at your possession. But we cannot understand that by just looking at the individual word that makes the above idiom. Moon says that idiom is "an ambiguous term used in conflicting ways"(3). In general use, idiom is a particular manner of expressing something in language, music, art, and so on which characterized a person or group. The dictionary of Linguistics and Phonetics defines idiom as a "sequence of words which are

semantically and often syntactically restricted, so that they function as single unit"(234). Some linguists refer to idiom as ready-made expression or utterances. The Longman Dictionary of English Idioms defines idioms as "a fixed group of words with special different meanings of the separate words"(732). According to The New Lexicon Webster Dictionary of English Language, idiom is "a language peculiar to people, country, class, community, or more rarely an individual, a construction, expression etc having meaning different from the literal one or not according to patterns of language"(567). Therefore, from this definition, one can say, idioms are a societal or community idiosyncrasy of the language. Idioms are metaphysical whose meanings cannot easily discerned by looking up the individual meaning of words in a ordinary dictionary. Because they are more or less invariable, both in wording and in certain grammatical ways, they cannot be changed or varied in a way literal expressions are normally varied. In linguistics, idioms are usually presumed to be figure of speech contradicting the principles of compositionality. That compositionality is the key notion to the analysis of idioms.

Language and Society

It is a known fact that there is no society without a language. In view of this, we can say a language cannot be separated from a society. Members of a society need language to express themselves. Therefore, one can however asserts that language and society have relationship. Longe has define language as "a system of arbitrary vocal symbols by which a group of people cooperate"(99). It is a vital instrument in cultural transmission and preservation as well as propagation of social group. To Fromkin and et'al, language is "a city to the building of which every human beings brought a stone and we live in a world of language"(55). This indicates that all human beings are stake or involved in it. Syal and Jindal sum it all by saying that "language is spacious-specie"(315). They further assert that all human beings are possessor of, at least, one language and language is found only in human. Wardhaugh opines that "when two or more people communicate with each other in speech, the system of communication they are

involved in it can be called a code. That code is something we call a language"(158). The ways in which language and society relate, in the opinion of Wardhaugh, have long intrigued researchers(169).

Society refers to "a complex web of human interactions and relationships that exist within a specific geographic area or among a group of people who share common interests, values, and norms", (Wardhaugh, 5). He further asserts that it is a collective entity comprising individuals who interact and cooperate with one another to meet their needs, fulfil their aspirations and establish a sense of belonging.

Society, according to the Collins Paperback Dictionary and Thesaurus, is seen as "a human being considered as a group in organized community. It is also an organized group with common aim and interests"(503). Trudgil asserts that linguists generally describe language as a rule-governed system which the member of a group habitually use in their daily interaction. This means that language users from different communities can be described by the language they speak. This is why, in the opinion of Hudson and Chambers contend that language is domesticated in society. Therefore, it is of necessity a code "(123).

Methodology

This paper adopts qualitative research approach in interrogating the relevance and significance of Hausa idioms in reflection of social order. It takes ethnographic approach which involves generating new insight by investigating specific attributes as evidently observed in the way people live and interact. The source of data collected for this paper is the Participant-observation method. It places the authors as a members of the society and enables them to obtain complete information in the context of use. The data was collected orally from the native Hausa speakers and translate those data into English for analysis. These data have been

presented to Hausa language expert in the department of Hausa of the Federal University Dutsin-Ma and he validates it as accurate as possible.

Analysis

The data are presented as an act sequence in Hausa and then translated into English. The analysis and typology will be given after which other ethnographic features of the SPEAKING mnemonic follow.

Datum 1

Act Sequence

Hausa: Tura gwaiwa ta hau kaya

English: To incite someone to do evil/bad

Analysis: This idiom refers to how someone is deceived into doing something which can be regretted later.

Typology: Didactic

Setting: Time and Place: in the evening/ at home

Scene: The father cautions his children against letting those who want to use their gullibility to incite them to do bad things.

Addresser: Father

Addressee: Son/daughter

End: To warn the children from those who want subdued them to evil.

Key: Serious and cautious tone

Datum 2:

Act Sequence

Hausa: Hannunka mai sanda

English: An indirect alert or notice

Analysis: This idiom suggests that someone is being guided indirectly on what to do.

Setting: Time and Place: in the afternoon/ at the courtroom

Scene: A judge was trying to make an accuser to realize that his behavior has grievous implications before the court.

Addresser: A judge

Addressee: A respondent/accuser

End: To advise/caution someone indirectly

Key: Serious tone

Datum 3

Act Sequence

Hausa: Hada karfi da karfe

English: To put synergy

Analysis: This idiom was drawn from Hausa worldview of unity and cooperation. No person is like an island in Hausa society.

Typology: Didactic/philosophical

Setting: Time and Place: in the evening/at village head's palace.

Scene: Village head addresses the community to be united and cooperative irrespective of the status.

Addresser: Village head

Addressee: Members of the community

End: To foster brotherhood and unity among the society.

Key: Serious and reflective tone

Datum 4

Act Sequence

Hausa: La'ilaha'ula'i

English Indecisiveness

Analysis: This idiom was drawn from the Hausa people intermingle with Islam. In fact, this phrase was from the Holy Book (Quran). It means one is wavering between two options or choices.

Typology: Analytical/Rhetorical

Setting: Time and Place: in the evening/on the pulpit

Scene: The scene here is an Image telling the congregants the history of some people. Despite all the terrible things that happened to them. They never wavered from their belief.

Addresser: Imam

Addressee: Congregation

End: To encourage the congregation to be firm in their faith.

Key: Serious tone

Datum 5

Act Sequence

Hausa: Haihata-haihatan

English: Forever/frequently or constantly

Analysis: This idiom, like that of number 4, was drawn from the mixed together of Hausa people with the Arabs and or Islam. In the context of use, it is applied in a thing which you would not do again.

Typology: Analytical/rhetorical

Setting: Time and Place: in the afternoon/ at home

Scene: The scene here is a husband/man telling his ex-wife who wants him to marry her that he would not remarry her.

Addresser: A man

Addressee: ex-wife

End: To reiterate the extent of the separation he had with her -- ex-wife.

Key: Serious tone.

Datum 6

Act Sequence

Hausa: Masu Ruwa da tsaki

English: Stakeholders or those responsible for something.

Analysis: This idiom is used to describe a parties involved in anything.

Typology: Rhetorical

Setting: Time and Place: in the evening/at the village head's palace.

Scene: the scene here is a meeting of those involved in maize farming.

Addressed: spokesperson

Addressee: audience

End: to reiterate the importance of being a functional member of society.

Key: serious.

Datum 7

Act Sequence

Hausa: Kan gwiwa

English: To be in the act of mother giving birth.

Analysis: This idiom describes the act of childbirth. The expectant mother usually squat on her knees while or during labour/childbirth.

Typology: Rhetorical/Analytical

Setting: Time and Place: in the evening/ at home.

Scene: the scene here is a husband narrating that his wife was in the birthing unit since yesterday.

Addressed: A man (husband).

Addressee: his friend.

End: to reiterate the situation of the expectant mother during childbirth.

Key: caring and pitiful tone.

Datum 8

Act Sequence

Hausa: Ba gudu ba ja da baya.

English: An unwavering determination and resilience.

Analysis: This idiom describes one's firmness or refusal to back down. It also suggests that one must endure in life no matter what comes at their way.

Typology: Philosophical/Didactic

Setting: Time and Place: in the evening/at home.

Scene: the scene here is an assembly. A leader is encouraging his subjects/subordinates not to accept defeat or retreat no matter what.

Addresser: A leader

Addressee: his followers

End: to encourage a followers to be firm and steadfast.

Key: serious and motivational tone.

Datum 9

Act Sequence

Hausa: Hannu Rabbana.

English: The poor or the needy.

Analysis: This idiom describes someone or people who beg for what to eat always. There is an adopted word - Rabbana - from Arabic which literally means Oh Lord, used while prayers or requisition.

Typology: Rhetorical

Setting: Time and Place: in the evening/at the wealthy man's house.

Scene: the scene here is an assemblage of haves-not in front yard of a rich man's house.

Addresser: a man

Addressee: his friend

End: to drive home the fact about people who lack basic needs of life.

Key: prayerful tone.

Datum 10

Act Sequence

Hausa: Wankin babban bargo.

English: To reprimand severely someone.

Analysis: This idiom is similar to English idiom "to rap someone over the knuckles". It means to criticize someone harshly. It alludes to how a blanket is washed thoroughly for being dirty.

Typology: Rhetorical/Analytical

Setting: Time and Place: in the evening/at the house of the most elderly person.

Scene: Here, the scene is one of the elders errs and the other elders censored him severely.

Addresser: The most elderly person

Addressee: erring elder

End: to inform the erring elder that what he does is unbecoming and unacceptable.

Key: Admonitory tone.

Discussion and Findings

The outcome of this discussion has provided an insight that the sociolinguistic implication of physical setting and or actual place where idioms are used is home. This indicates that Hausa people do not only regards the home as the nucleus of the society but also a place where aspects of Hausa culture and language can be learned. The physical and temporal settings for the use of idioms are sociolinguistically and socioculturally suitable.

For participants, furthermore, the sociolinguistic implication is that typical Hausa society is male dominated. However, in rare occasions, women are expected to speak.

In addition, the sociolinguistic implication of the End is that seriousness is attached to idioms in speech delivery in Hausa culture.

Typology underscores the sociolinguistic use of idioms in speech delivery in Hausa oratory.

In conclusion, the data reflect aspect of Hausa worldview of language and culture as supported by Sapir-Whorf. Datum 3 describes Hausa worldview of unity, cooperation, and oneness. Then data 4, 5 and 9 illustrate the language borrowing (adoption) which indicates that Hausa language can continue to be alive. It would not go into extinction.

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